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MODERN METHODS OF TREATING CEREBRAL PALSY

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Treatment of cerebral palsy is a long and difficult process, and the participation of several specialists is considered necessary. In this case, it is considered advisable to involve a rehabilitation specialist, neurologist, art therapist, occupational therapist, kinesiologist, massage therapist, speech pathologist, pediatrician, deaf-mute therapist and a number of other specialists. Of course, parental involvement is considered very effective for homeschooling. Parental participation creates inner peace and confidence in the child and ensures long-term continuation of this rehabilitation. At this stage, we must not forget about drug treatment. If you put it all together, long-term, ongoing rehabilitation will certainly show its results.

Key words: attractiveness, effective method, continuous rehabilitation, strong confidence, inner peace, home environment

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СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ ДЕТСКОГО ЦЕРЕБРАЛЬНОГО ПАРАЛИЧА

Лечение ДЦП – длительный и трудный процесс, и участие нескольких специалистов считается необходимостью. При этом считается целесообразным привлечение врача-реабилитолога, невролога, арт-терапевта,

эрготерапевта, кинезиолога, массажиста, дефектолога, педиатра, глухонемого терапевта и ряда других специалистов. Конечно, участие родителей считается очень эффективным для домашних занятий. Участие родителей создает у ребенка внутренний покой и уверенность и обеспечивает долгосрочное продолжение этой реабилитации. На этом этапе нельзя забывать о медикаментозном лечении. Если сложить все это вместе, долгосрочная, непрерывная реабилитация, безусловно, не преминет показать свои результаты.

Ключевые слова: привлекательность, эффективный метод, непрерывная реабилитация, сильная уверенность, внутренний мир, домашняя обстановка

The life of patients with cerebral palsy consists of a combination of various aspects of rehabilitation: rehabilitation, physical and psychological, social, emotional and educational processes.[6] Recently, attention has been paid to new organizational forms in the complex rehabilitation system. Among them, the game method of teaching the child everyday skills is of great interest.

The purpose of the research is to develop and scientifically base a new organizational form and system of open games in combination with other non-traditional means for teaching daily skills to children with the consequences of cerebral palsy.

Research methods: children aged 3 to 10 years with the consequences of cerebral palsy in the late residual stage. Before starting rehabilitation activities, it is necessary to determine the initial severity of movement disorders in order to properly plan and rationally organize classes. Rehabilitation training should match the child's capabilities, support the motivation of children with cerebral palsy to continue training, and create a comfortable emotional environment. For children with cerebral palsy, the program of rehabilitation and restorative effects of teaching the child daily skills through physical education and sports helps to solve the following problems:

- improving walking skills;
- improve balance and coordination of movements;
- development of hand-eye coordination;
- development of fine motor skills of hands;

- development of the emotional and volitional sphere;
- development of spatial movement directions
- to practice qualitatively and strengthen previously acquired motor skills and abilities.

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In the initial stages of rehabilitation and recovery activities, we consider the most effective individual method of working with a child, in the future training with children should be conducted using different methods: individual, small group and group. In addition to the generally recognized means and forms of physical education and sports, it is recommended to include non-traditional exposure methods in the complex system of rehabilitation and recovery measures to teach the child daily skills, for example:

- computer educational games;
- psychogymnastics.

The game method of conducting lessons consisting of various game situations, tasks, exercises and games was widely used to solve correction problems. When playing sports, children with spastic diplegia need special exercises that help strengthen the back muscles, relax the adductor muscles of the thighs, and overcome postural reflexes. A distinctive feature of the developed methodology of rehabilitation and recreational activities is the differentiation of all means and forms of rehabilitation, outdoor and sports games, which are used according to the form of the disease and the degree of motor impairment. Implementation and effectiveness of rehabilitation and health measures for children with the consequences of cerebral palsy can only be carried out under systematic medical supervision. A training system has been developed using non-traditional forms of rehabilitation and rehabilitation activities, including computer correction games for children with cerebral palsy, in addition to outdoor and sports games.

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The pedagogical experience we conducted and the obtained results made it possible to scientifically justify the effectiveness of the complex methodology of rehabilitation and recreational effects.

Summary. According to the literature, the practice of using existing methods and tools for the rehabilitation of cerebral palsy is not effective enough, which predetermines the search for new approaches, tools, methods and forms for the successful implementation of rehabilitation and recreational activities. The nature of the impact of rehabilitation on the body of a child with the consequences of cerebral palsy should be comprehensive, rehabilitation and recreation activities should take into account the mechanisms of rehabilitation and compensation as the biological basis of the recovery process, and support the motivation of disabled people. children for continuous activity, conducting classes in a mode suitable for the child's capabilities, creating a comfortable psychological background. The complex system of rehabilitation effects used in our work consisted of:

- special physical exercises with targeted effect;
- physical exercises with elements of gymnastics;
- game activity with a focused effect;
- sports and outdoor games;
- computer educational games;
- psycho-gymnastics course.

The main focus of our work is the game method. In addition to traditional game methods, we also used a whole group of relatively new promising methods of working with children of this group: the method of music and rhythm therapy; the method of simulating animals and plants, the method of "theater of physical education".

The results of physical rehabilitation of disabled children showed high efficiency, which was reflected in the improvement of their mobility.

The results of entertainment and rehabilitation activities also had a positive effect on the mental state of disabled children with cerebral palsy. The following data illustrates this:

- in the experimental group, when the test was conducted on the individual's differential scale on the individual's power factor, the differences were significant and amounted to 28%. The differences found in the control group were not significant, the personal power factor improved by 9%.

Thus, the complex system of recreational and rehabilitation activities has shown its effectiveness in teaching daily skills to children with cerebral palsy and can be recommended for use in practical work with disabled people with consequences of cerebral palsy.

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